

Policy and market reform recommendations for the successful acceptance of advanced data-driven solutions in the energy sector in Europe

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, energy markets in Europe are being hit by great volatility and uncertainty, due to the energy supply shortage from Russian sources and the post-pandemic economic crisis. This new environment has made necessary the enactment of new regulations affecting the EU energy policy to reduce dependence of Russian energy supply and speed up the renewable energy uptake and energy efficiency targets in Europe.

Artificial Intelligence and data-driven powerful analytics on energy usage are widely used to support decision making about energy consumption in buildings and communities. The research presented in this paper makes an analysis of socio-economic and regulatory obstacles to innovative digital energy management solutions, with the aim to provide addressable recommendations for policy makers and market players. The objective is to identify plausible policy changes and market reform recommendations that enable a smooth implementation of data-driven business models and AI solutions in the energy markets. These markets include heat and electricity retail and distribution markets, Demand Response aggregation, and Energy Efficiency markets. The massive use of data for the deployment of the digital solutions also imposes regulation changes in data exchange markets.

The paper focuses on the European-wide regulatory framework with specific country-related barriers caused by partial or late transposition of the existing directives into national legislation. Policy and market reform analysis covers different areas of recommendation including market openness and democracy, market fairness, data protection and standardization, energy efficiency in buildings, grid infrastructure management, energy communities and urban infrastructure planning.

The final conclusions and recommendations are useful not only to relevant European Policy Makers, but they can also help technology developers of innovative data-driven solutions in the energy sector.

KEYWORDS

Data-driven solutions, Market reform recommendations, Regulatory barriers, Data transaction market, Energy market, Energy service market.

INTRODUCTION

The European Union, in pursuit of its energy transition targets, has been affected by the post-pandemic economic crisis and the 80% shortage of Russian gas supply during the last few years. These events have disrupted the energy system, leading to faster integration of renewable energy sources into the electric mix due to gas unavailability. Furthermore, the volatility in energy prices has caused a skyrocketing effect on energy markets across Europe. For example, Member States registered a price increase of 200% to 300% during 2022 compared to 2021, due to influence of gas pipelines cut-off in wholesale electricity marginal price [1] s. As a result, some customers must stop their consumption. On the other hand, fully financial support from governments is not a sustainable policy in the long term. Therefore, a new price balance,

to leverage benefits for both data producers and data consumers in each of the markets under analysis: data transaction market, energy market and energy efficiency services market.

BARRIERS TO THE MARKET UPTAKE OF INNOVATIVE DATA-DRIVEN ENERGY SOLUTIONS

The main market barriers exposed in this chapter have been identified by business and market players in each of the target markets, data transaction market, energy markets and energy services market. Other barriers have been elicited during the demonstration activities in the living labs of the EC-funded H2020 BEYOND project. The project aims at creating and deploying advanced data analytics and algorithms for efficient energy and asset management based on real-time data collection and consumption.

DATA TRANSACTION MARKET

New technologies in the use and analysis of data such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) are increasingly present in all areas. Artificial Intelligence uses machine learning techniques on large volumes of data, robotics and automated decision-making systems to simulate human behaviour and reasoning and make autonomous decisions. Unfortunately, up to now there is not specific regulation about Artificial Intelligence technologies to limit or expand their increasing impact on society[8]–[10]. Indeed, there is no regulated mechanisms or compliance bodies to certify the transparency and security of AI and this creates mistrust among data producers to share their data with energy service providers.

At present, there are restrictions in data sharing for the avoidance of data misuse beyond the initially intended scope. The user information processed should be private and its misuse may compromise the end user, which may lead to restrictions on the use of data, when it comes to the collection, processing, and analysis of personal data of prosumers.

Another important barrier for the use of energy data in buildings is the collection of the metering data on real-time, as the current smart-meter rollout programmes have been carried out and belong to distributors and third parties that do not share this data with data service providers, at least not on real-time bases.

However, the main barrier in terms of data transaction from buildings, is the lack of a general (overall) semantic model equivalent to IEC CIM (Common Information Model adopted by the International Electrotechnical Commission) in the electric grids, or, in a different sense to the Brick Ontology or other ontologies built on top of tagging models, that would directly cover the whole value chain. Moreover, many buildings and energy domain standards and ontologies utilize strict ontological relations which means that the user needs to comply with the selection of abstractions in the standards. Any additions in the ontology require an amendment of ontological definition and strict placement of new class within the modelling ontology.

Table 1 summarises the main barriers of the energy data transaction and management.

Table 1 Barriers in the data transaction and management

BARRIER	
DATA TRANSACTION	Metering data provision from 3rd parties
	Lack of common data semantic model in the electricity grids (interoperability)

Lack of standard compatibility
Data collection and sharing restrictions to avoid data misuse and ensure personal data privacy compliance
Lack of regulated mechanisms and compliance bodies for certifying the transparency and security of AI

ENERGY MARKETS

At present, in most EU member states, the electricity distribution market is liberalised but, in fact, it is closed to new competitors and actors. This activity is often carried out in markets operated by a single player or with very short market competition. Competition is allowed but in reality, the high entry barriers leave low chance for new incomers to compete against existing actors. In addition, investing in fully-fledged new distribution networks is unaffordable and economically not interesting for the electricity system.

Regarding the knowledge about users' data there is a certain opacity on the part of the actors performing the metering. Large energy market retailers counting on a large customer base may use aggregated data for better energy demand forecasts to play in the day-ahead markets and are reluctant to lose this competitive advantage with respect to their market competitors. Moreover, access to submetering data, like the demand of specific loads in a building (air conditioning, heating, Domestic Hot Water (DHW)) is not possible unless installing the necessary dedicated metering equipment on premises with prior consent by the building resident. The necessary associated data private gateway and internet secure connection is also needed.

Over the years, technologies improve, and process digitalization takes place, entailing large cultural and behavioural changes. Fear to these developments might delay the change from the traditional to the modern digital energy distribution network. Furthermore, energy consumers need to be fitted with smart metering devices. The cost of these devices can be a barrier if they are to be borne by the energy consumers. In buildings, smart meters roll out has been done on the expenses of the distribution companies but then data remains in their premises and cannot be accessed on real-time basis.

National digitalisation standards in the Member States' electricity systems are missing or not aligned with a European-wide network data standardisation[11]. This makes difficult the integration of the different national distribution networks into a pan-European common network to give room to a wider cross-border energy transaction and flexibility.

From the demand response side, energy markets are mainly closed to aggregated explicit demand response in many Member States. TSO and DSO do not have the capacity to operate local flexibility markets to buy the flexibility they need to avoid congestions and manage their distribution grids in a more efficient manner [12]. Similarly, TSO and DSOs lack the appropriate infrastructure to send automated real-time signals to buildings' dispatchable loads to allow for an explicit real-time demand response,

Regarding renewable sources, the current high and increasing contribution of wind power and photovoltaic power in today's energy systems in Europe brings up the problem of what to do with the increasing energy surplus when climatic conditions allow for a high generation rate, above the system consumption level (sunny and windy days). Albeit some storage is already available in reversible hydro power plants and batteries, the storage capacity is still too low to store these high amounts of energy that, finally, must be curtailed lowering the new RES

facility economic feasibility. Moreover, the soaring growth of renewable energy generation is creating congestion problems in the network with a current shortage of available energy transport bandwidth in the high and medium voltage networks. This is now limiting a further expansion of RES new facilities and hence, jeopardising the EU’s ambitious decarbonisation targets for 2030 and 2050.

Grid balancing issues are expected to increase as more renewable generation capacity is installed. Network System Operators use advanced demand forecasting tools to predict the day ahead generation plan. These calculation engines use climatic weather forecasts, and historic consumption data, along with corrections applicable to the type of day and season of the year and obtain reasonably accurate demand predictions for the day-ahead plan. Nevertheless, the higher contribution to the demand consumption by RES self-consumption units the larger the prediction uncertainty of Grid net demand covered by non-distributed sources. This puts a higher pressure on the balancing and ancillary services to match net demand and generation that can hardly be managed by manageable generation sources.

The type of centralised versus distributed new renewable energy generation plants also poses additional pressure on the energy distribution networks. Large solar photovoltaic plants (50 MW) are usually more profitable than small size generation plants in per-kW terms due to the economies of scale for high volume purchasing and lower maintenance costs. In order to promote self-consumption, new regulations greatly simplify the registration procedures for off-grid generation units, as well as for very small units ($P < 10$ kWp). This is enough for single dwelling self-consumption but does not cover a vast number of generation units meant for shared self-consumption of large buildings, neighbourhoods, districts or energy communities. In the particular case of Spain, legal procedures are simplified for facilities as far as 100 kWp. Plants with peak power above 100 kWp are not allowed to have their surplus compensated, the only alternative being the direct sales to the wholesale spot market. This is a barrier for shared energy facilities in energy communities or large building blocks. In addition, plants above 10 kWp must obtain DSO prior permission, delaying approval lead times beyond what is reasonable.

Finally, energy directives for energy communities and shared self-consumption is not fully transposed into national regulation in some countries[13], [14].

A summary of the main barriers identified in energy markets is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Energy Markets Barriers

BARRIER	
ENERGY MARKETS	Electricity Distribution market is, in fact, closed to new competitors and actors.
	Personal metering data privacy.
	Opacity on the part of the agents. No data sharing.
	Smart metering rollout and cost.
	Consumer environmental awareness. Energy Market closed to small consumers and citizens.
	Access to BTM data requirements
	Lack of national digitalisation standards for the Electricity System.
	Energy markets closed to explicit aggregated demand flexibility.

Lack of the appropriate infrastructure from TSO to send in Real-Time the dispatchable loads.
Energy regulation transposition for energy communities and shared self-consumption.
Inertia to change traditional network operation in favour of digitalization.
Energy Market structure mainly favours economic feasibility on large RES facilities
Grid high and medium voltage development needed for greater RES growth.
Self-consumption facilities huge bureaucratic burden for registration if P>100kW.
PV growth increases uncertainty in demand forecast for DSO/TSO.
Delays in energy storage alternatives may end up in high curtailment levels, lowering the new facility feasibility.

ENERGY SERVICE MARKET

The energy services market involves the use of a large volume of private data belonging to energy consumers and hence, requires the utmost care and transparency in data management. Energy consumption data, information on installed equipment and environmental and occupancy sensors, combined with information from smart meters, can reveal personal consumption profiles. Data protection and privacy considerations for data sharing is an important barrier to be addressed or considered in this sector.

ESCOs are the energy service providers, usually registered in the national ESCO registries. The registration is voluntary and the ESCOs are subcategorized based on the companies' own transcript of historic records of energy efficiency projects. This lack of verified information regarding the registered ESCOs has created mistrust for the quality of their services. This is a structural barrier which has significantly delayed the implementation of large-scale Energy Performance projects in some countries.

ESCOs in the building and residential sector are reluctant to tie their revenues to performance metrics due to the high investment risks, the low acceptance of valid verification procedures and the uncertainty of future energy market prices. Continuous changes in the energy market policies and regulations also hinder the signing of long-term service contracts. Although most of the ESCO contracts are Energy Performance Contracts (EPC) tied to the achievement of energy savings, there is not a mandatory use of Performance Measurement and Verification (PMV) protocols and a lack of a reliable PMV standard.

Finally, there is a new concept that has been created by the European Union, which is the Energy Communities, either Citizen Energy Communities (CEC) or Renewable Energy Communities (REC)[15], [16]. Energy communities can also play a role in the energy efficiency market ensuring a higher market uptake, a greater involvement of citizens in the pursuit of energy efficiency goals and a collective participation in community-level sustainability projects. The proper transposition of these entities in the national regulatory framework is a priority that need to be pushed forward with immediate effect.

A summary of the barriers identified in the energy service market is listed in Table 3.

Table 3 Energy Service Market Barriers

BARRIER

ENERGY SERVICE MARKET	Data protection and privacy for data sharing.
	Barriers to adoption of data sharing solutions for EE in buildings.
	Market democracy, fairness and awareness raising.
	Empowering consumers' energy communities.
	Mistrust between the client and the ESCOs due to lack of information in the ESCO registry
	ESCOs are reluctant to invest in Energy Performance Services due the high risk and the lack of appropriate PMV standards

POLICY MARKET REFORMS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Following the identification and analysis of barriers, this paper seeks to provide regulatory and market reform recommendations that would help the deployment of new data-driven solutions in all markets, namely the data transaction market, the energy supply market and the energy services market.

DATA TRANSACTION MARKET

About data availability an important recommendation is the establishment of an appropriate data market, capable of carrying out data transactions between data consumer, data providers and data owners close to real time and historical data used by a third party for billing services. Additionally, another recommendation is to enable secure alternative data paths to collect data from building level and support the establishment of data hubs.

In the field of data interoperability, authorities should ensure that different existing standards be mutually compatible and have conversions and mappings between themselves. Similarly, data models should allow for extensibility as it is not reasonable to think of an ontological model today that would work for all future applications, the extension mechanisms and handling of model upgrades should be provided.

Data sharing needs are to be performed on the basis of formalised processes that can be effectively monitored, both addressing access control over the data, but also effective auditing of its use by other parties. A robust framework regulating data sharing and marketplaces is currently missing and is introduced in very detail in the anticipated Data Governance Act.

Finally, it was mentioned the lack of an AI regulation. This regulation should observe the AI ethical guidelines:

a) Human agency and oversight: by empowering humans to make informed decisions using AI-enabled applications that always involve the human-in-command and preserve human agency even in automated actions.

b) Technical Robustness and safety: by offering resilient and secure solutions that ensure accuracy and reliability when used.

c) Privacy and data governance: by ensuring enhanced protection of data privacy and confidentiality while applying robust data governance mechanisms for ensuring the high quality and integrity of data processed.

d) Transparency: by making aware humans that they are interacting with an AI-enabled system.

e) Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness: by being accessible to all, regardless of any disability, and in a non-discriminatory manner.

f) Societal and environmental well-being: by focusing on decarbonization of energy systems and enabling the proper balancing of this objective with the well-being and comfort of humans/ prosumers.

g) Accountability: by continuously monitoring and assessing the performance of algorithms, data, and pipelines designed and effectively improving them in a transparent manner.

Based on the above AI Ethics guidelines, the Artificial Intelligence Act needs to be put in action so as to provide the means and certification schemes for AI systems. In turn, AI systems need to enable the assessment of model transparency aspects and ensure immunity and technical robustness of AI models through appropriate security mechanisms for detecting malicious activities and bias introduced in AI results.

Market regulatory authorities must monitor that market actors provide and use technical tools and techniques to prevent data and security breaches. They must ensure compliance with GDPR about data privacy and protection and minimise reported data loss threats and data sharing issues. These techniques include authentication, anonymisation, pseudonymisation, data encryption, data aggregation and the use of security standard protocols.

The main recommendations in the data transaction market and AI are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4 Data Transaction Market Recommendations

RECOMMENDATIONS	
DATA MARKET	Establishment of an appropriate data market, for close to real time data transactions between data consumer, data providers and data owners.
	Market authorities should ensure that the overall semantic model be interoperable with the legacy systems at all levels and all areas of coverage, keeping or adding the semantic information of external data without making the system intractable at big data scale.
	Different existing standards shall be mutually compatible and have conversions and mappings between themselves.
	A robust framework regulating data sharing and marketplaces is currently missing and shall be introduced in very detail in the anticipated Data Governance Act.
	Artificial Intelligence Act needs to be put in action so as to provide the means and certification schemes for AI systems. In turn, AI systems need to enable the assessment of model transparency aspects and ensure immunity and technical robustness of AI models through appropriate security mechanisms for detecting malicious activities and bias introduced in AI results.

ENERGY MARKETS

Energy markets include all commercial activities carried out by the different market players in the energy sector. The transport and distribution market should be reformed to pull down the entrance barriers to new competitors, by allowing them to use the existing networks to provide distribution services to their customers. Commercial agreements to pay for the usage of the existing network should be promoted to maximise the usage rate of the existing assets and reduce their long payback periods. A neutral market authority should ensure this competition takes place in a fair basis.

Regulation authorities should be observant about the transparency in the information sharing among different market actors, regardless of their size. In the same way, regulators should enforce metering companies to make their clients' data available on their request to allow them to benefit from their own data by contracting with service providers the delivery of valuable energy and non-energy services.

Democratization of energy markets is also a key regulatory target. Market structure should integrate citizens by allowing them to participate in the system as energy community members, demand response programmes and P2P energy trading, either directly or by means of aggregation and representation services. For this purpose, correct price signals and low energy volume thresholds to enter in the market is a "must".

Authorities should also incentivize the digitization of buildings and facilities, thus valorising users' data with lower initial investments. They should promote the measurement and reporting of metrics such as the Smart Readiness Index to assess how well buildings are prepared to deliver data and integrate automatisms for explicit DR and energy efficiency programmes.

In terms of regulatory barriers, the current impossibility of demand side aggregators to take part actively in energy markets in many EU countries is a major hindrance. Flexibility services should be a cost-effective alternative to network infrastructure investments. Regulatory authorities should work on the development of a regulatory framework to allow distribution system operators to create and promote local flexibility markets and exploit them to delay or reduce costly grid investment decisions and avoid congestions in their networks.

In the same way, regulatory authorities should approve specifications and market products for the procurement of demand side services for congestion management and grid balancing services in equal terms than generation side products. Similarly, they should incentivise and encourage the deployment of local flexibility resources and the participation in research projects.

Regulations should promote Market-based, transparent and participatory process through which distribution system operators can procure flexibility services from all sources, with the recognition of independent aggregators as market active actors without the consent of other market participants.

Market signals for implicit demand response are still too weak to be effective. Explicit demand response is a more reliable and precise source of demand flexibility but for it to be real, it is necessary to promote the development of interoperable remote-control and automation systems for dispatchable loads that make part of a DR aggregation contract for direct and easy load management on real – time to comply with grid operator (TSO) requirements.

The current legislation does not fully favour the creation of energy communities, with complicated concepts and procedures that make end users feel some rejection to the deployment of communities and continue to bet on previous models such as shared self-consumption. Regarding this, the main aspects to define in the regulation transposition are:

- Remove administrative barriers and promote the fair and transparent registration and licensing procedures related to use grid permissions.
- Define the type of legal entity that should represent the energy community.

- Promote finance incentives to support the development of RECs.
- Promote the deployment of information tools to improve the consumer awareness and motivate them to become part of RECs.
- Establish DSO duties to ensure the cooperation with RECs in terms of its integration into the distribution network, and thus act as neutral market facilitator.

On the field of RES development, it is important to bet on decentralised energy resources. In this way, regulators should simplify the registration procedures for smaller size RES plants to avoid huge facilities of non-distributed generation with high environmental impact and important grid congestion problems. Incentives to smaller size facilities, usually more expensive in per-kW terms, would also be a positive measure. These incentives may be offered in the form of an extension of the surplus compensation schemes to units greater than 100 kW that are meant for self-consumption on sharing basis for more than one consumer, and for energy communities. The reluctance of DSO to grant connection permits can be mitigated by duly compensating them for the usage of their grids by small self-consumption units.

Finally, the electricity system of the future will need to rely on new and innovative large-capacity energy storage technologies like green hydrogen, Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) protocols to maximise the benefits of a growing electric vehicle stock and the smart use of the buildings thermal energy as a mean to store energy at a large scale.

The Energy market reform recommendations are listed in Table 5.

Table 5 Energy Markets Recommendations

RECOMMENDATIONS	
ENERGY MARKET	Market should be reformed to pull down the entrance barriers to new market players, by allowing them to use the existing networks to provide distribution services to their customers. Commercial agreements to pay for the usage of the existing network.
	Market regulatory authorities must monitor that market actors provide and use technical tools and techniques to prevent data and security breaches.
	Legislative reform to achieve transparency in the contracts between the parties involved.
	Regulation should enforce metering companies to make their clients' data available on their request to allow for the contracting and provision of valuable energy and non-energy services by third parties, thus reducing the cost on additional equipment needed to collect these metering data.
	Regulation should focus on issues such as carbon footprint, energy efficiency and developing new business models for end-users. Moreover, the market structure must integrate users by allowing them to participate in the system as an energy community, demand response programs and P2P trading.
	Incentivize the digitization of buildings and facilities, thus obtaining user data with lower initial investments.
	Deploy the common European Network Codes throughout the European Union's Member State.
	Define an aggregation model adapted to the European electricity market.
	Develop a regulatory framework to promote the flexibility of distribution system operators.

Approve specifications and market products for the procurement of flexibility services as well as incentivise and encourage the deployment of local flexibility resources and participation in research projects. Flexibility services should be a cost-effective alternative to network infrastructure investments.

Boost the digitalization of buildings to allow direct real-time metering, data storage and safeguarding data sharing, to include not only billing metering but also DER metering data.

Promote the development of interoperable remote-control and automation systems for dispatchable loads that make part of a DR aggregation contract for direct and easy load management on real – time to comply with grid operator requirements.

Current legislation does not fully support the creation of energy communities, with complicated concepts and procedures.

Grid operation has been carried out in a similar way over the last decades, with few improvements to manage present and future changes in consumption or decentralised generation.

Simplify the registration procedures for smaller size RES plants to avoid huge facilities of non-distributed generation with high environmental impact and important grid congestion problems. Give incentives to smaller size facilities.

Give incentives to smaller size facilities, give incentives to transporting and distribution companies to enlarge the current networks.

ENERGY SERVICE MARKET

It is important to introduce appropriate mechanisms for increasing transparency in energy market transactions and reinforcing trust of consumers / prosumers and increase awareness of the benefits of data sharing for the provision of advanced energy services. EC's funded demonstration projects can be a good way to show users the benefits of advanced data-driven tools and algorithms.

The national ESCO registry should be better organised and controlled with a fairer classification of the ESCOs providing enough information about the activities and the projects of each company. This registry should be managed and controlled by National Energy Agencies or Governmental Energy Departments, and the past-experience records checked against actual data to guarantee truthfulness.

EPC contracts should be promoted by means of exemplary public contracts for energy efficiency. Incentives to this type of energy service contracting should be granted by National regulators and National Energy Agencies. Governments should simplify the Public Tenders and facilitate the participation of ESCOs in public projects. This can be done by splitting large and complex EPC contracts into smaller scope contracts covering specific buildings and even building energy demands.

Existence and promotion of clear, fair and accurate protocols of measurement and verification ought to be proposed and suggested by regulatory entities to allow for a transparent and standard measurement of energy performance that brings trust to the EPC service contracting, getting it closer to a Pay-for-Performance (P4P) modality.

Finally, energy market regulations should have a longer validation period to increase stability in the energy regulation framework. New regulations should be designed in a way that they give continuity to the legal framework, constructing upon existing directives and providing a long-term scope for the new markets. Fossil fuel independence from external

sources outside the EU can greatly contribute to isolate the European energy markets from worldwide energy supply crisis, like the Russian-Ukraine recent conflict.

Table 6 shows the summary of the main energy service market reform recommendations.

Table 6 Energy Service Market Recommendations

RECOMMENDATIONS	
ENERGY SERVICE MARKET	Good knowledge and sensitivity about GDPR when sharing data and try to take data protection regulations into account from the very beginning of data collection and sharing.
	Developing and simplifying tools that support the development of individual projects and adapting existing tools to reduce barriers to use.
	Need to introduce appropriate mechanisms for increasing transparency in energy market transactions and reinforcing trust of consumers / prosumers.
	Establish an operational energy renaissance model that aims to improve the energy efficiency of the privately owned building stock by providing energy consultancy expertise.
	The national ESCO registry should be better organised with a fairer classification of the ESCOs providing enough information about the activities and the projects of each member.
	The national ESCO registry should be better organised with a fairer classification of the ESCOs providing enough information about the activities and the projects of each company. This registry should be managed and controlled by National Energy Agencies or Governmental Energy Departments.
	EPC contracts should be promoted by means of exemplary public contracts for energy efficiency. Incentives to this type of energy service contracting should be granted by National regulators and National Energy Agencies.
Existence and promotion of clear, fair, and accurate protocols of measurement and verification ought to be proposed and suggested by regulatory entities. Governments should simplify the Public Tenders and facilitate the participation of ESCOs in public projects. Energy market regulations should have a longer validation period to increase stability in the energy regulation framework.	

CONCLUSION

By means of an exhaustive review of the existing regulatory framework at European and national levels and the relevant feedback from market active players through structured interviews and end user surveys a detailed analysis of the regulatory and market barriers impeding the deployment of innovative data-driven solutions in the energy sector. The experience gathered in the demonstration activities of the EU-funded BEYOND project have been very useful too.

The market and regulatory reform recommendations, stemming from market inefficiencies and incomplete implementation or transposition of current European directives, address each of the analysed markets. The analysed markets are the data market in terms of data protection, transaction and standardization, energy markets including distribution, generation, ancillary services, and demand flexibility, and energy service markets providing efficiency services to buildings, companies, and city authorities.

Among the main recommendations proposed for the data market the most relevant in the current regulatory framework are the real-time metering data availability prior consent of the consumers and the necessary standardization of data and communication protocols. The availability of this energy data can trigger privacy issues, so in this respect it would be desirable to establish a proper data market with a robust framework for data sharing and marketplaces, which currently does not exist as a structured market, and which is introduced in detail in the anticipated Data Governance Act.

Related with energy markets, many recommendations can be made in a variety of topics. We underline those that have to do with market openness in energy markets, and specially for aggregated demand response; the creation of local demand flexibility markets run by DSOs and TSOs where they can purchase the demand side flexibility needed for congestion management and grid balancing. In this regard, policymakers should have transparency on price signals and low energy volume thresholds in mind to encourage new prosumers to enter the market, while also simplifying the administrative procedures. Finally, due to the present and future increase of renewable energies in recent times, the creation of energy and citizen communities for self-consumption should be well regulated across Europe following the European directives. A correct supervision and compensation of the distribution companies to give a timely response to requests related to the allocation of connection nodes for these new installations would promote private investments in self-consumption assets for a future decentralised electricity grid.

Related to the energy service markets, the main recommendations include the proposition of open access hybrid and fair performance and verification methodologies to assess energy performance. By doing so, transparency in energy market transactions and strengthen consumer / prosumer confidence would be promoted.

The proper implementation of these recommendations in today's regulatory framework would greatly help to shape the digitalisation and smart use of data in Europe's future energy system.

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NOMENCLATURE

Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
BtM	Behind the Meter
CEC	Citizen Energy Communities
EE	Energy Efficiency
DR	Demand Response
EPC	Energy Performance Contracting
CIM	Common Information Model
DHW	Domestic Heat Water
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication, and trust Services
DSO	Distribution System Operator
ESCOs	Energy Services Companies

EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IoT	Internet of Things
PV	Photovoltaic
REC	Renewable Energy Communities
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
TSO	Transmission System Operator

REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission, “Quarterly report On European electricity markets Market Observatory for Energy DG Energy,” 2023.
- [2] M. Montakhabi, S. van der Graaf, and M. A. Mustafa, “Valuing the value: An affordances perspective on new models in the electricity market,” *Energy Research and Social Science*, vol. 96. Elsevier Ltd, Feb. 01, 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.erss.2022.102902.
- [3] J. Rosenow, “Europe on the way to net zero: What challenges and opportunities?,” *PLOS Climate*, vol. 1, no. 7, p. e0000058, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.1371/journal.pclm.0000058.
- [4] J. Cifuentes-Faura, “European Union policies and their role in combating climate change over the years,” *Air Quality, Atmosphere and Health*, vol. 15, no. 8. Springer Science and Business Media B.V., pp. 1333–1340, Aug. 01, 2022. doi: 10.1007/s11869-022-01156-5.
- [5] IEEE Power & Energy Society. and Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, *2020 17th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM)*.
- [6] Y. K. Dwivedi *et al.*, “Artificial Intelligence (AI): Multidisciplinary perspectives on emerging challenges, opportunities, and agenda for research, practice and policy,” *Int J Inf Manage*, vol. 57, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.08.002.
- [7] S. Tagliapietra *et al.*, “An assessment of Europe’s options for addressing the crisis in energy markets,” 2022.
- [8] E. Fournier-Tombs, “Towards a United Nations Internal Regulation for Artificial Intelligence,” *Big Data Soc*, vol. 8, no. 2, 2021, doi: 10.1177/20539517211039493.
- [9] L. Vesnic-Alujevic, S. Nascimento, and A. Pólvara, “Societal and ethical impacts of artificial intelligence: Critical notes on European policy frameworks,” *Telecomm Policy*, vol. 44, no. 6, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.telpol.2020.101961.
- [10] W. Hoffmann-Riem, “Artificial Intelligence as a Challenge for Law and Regulation,” in *Regulating Artificial Intelligence*, Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020, pp. 1–29. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-32361-5_1.
- [11] L. de Mello and Ter-Minassian Teresa, “Digitalisation Challenges and Opportunities for Subnational Governments,” 2020.
- [12] O. Valarezo *et al.*, “Analysis of new flexibility market models in Europe,” *Energies*, vol. 14, no. 12. MDPI AG, Jun. 02, 2021. doi: 10.3390/en14123521.

- [13] D. Frieden, A. Tuerk, J. Roberts, S. D’Herbement, A. F. Gubina, and B. Komel, “Overview of emerging regulatory frameworks on collective self-consumption and energy communities in Europe,” in *2019 16th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM)*, IEEE, Sep. 2019, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/EEM.2019.8916222.
- [14] D. Frieden *et al.*, “Collective self-consumption and energy communities: Trends and challenges in the transposition of the EU framework,” 2019.
- [15] C. D’Alpaos and F. Andreolli, “Renewable energy communities: The challenge for new policy and regulatory frameworks design,” in *Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies*, Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH, 2021, pp. 500–509. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-48279-4_47.
- [16] C. Inês, P. L. Guilherme, M. G. Esther, G. Swantje, H. Stephen, and H. Lars, “Regulatory challenges and opportunities for collective renewable energy prosumers in the EU,” *Energy Policy*, vol. 138, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2019.111212.